

ADOPTION GAP IN BT COTTON CULTIVATION

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Abstract:

Bt cotton is an important fibers crop contributing significantly to the agricultural economy of India, particularly in Maharashtra where cotton cultivation occupies a major area. However, the productivity of Bt cotton at the farm level often remains below its potential due to incomplete adoption of recommended cultivation practices. The present investigation was undertaken in Amravati district of Maharashtra during 2024–25 to examine the extent of adoption gap, yield gap, and socio-economic determinants of Bt cotton cultivation. A multistage random sampling procedure was employed to select 120 Bt cotton growers from 12 villages of Daryapur and Anjangaon surji tahsils. Data were gathered through a structured interview schedule and analyzed using descriptive statistics along with Pearson's correlation. Findings indicated that most farmers were old-aged, owned small land holdings, and had medium levels of income, knowledge, innovativeness, and risk orientation. Overall adoption of recommended Bt cotton practices was moderate; however, Noticeable gaps were observed in practices such as sowing method, application of FYM, and intercultural operations. The yield index reflected a yield shortfall of about 30–40% between research station potential and field-level performance. Correlation results revealed that education, income, source of information, and innovativeness significantly influenced the level of adoption. Farmers reported several constraints such as high cost of fertilizers, lack of technical knowledge, untimely weather information, and shortage of labour. The study suggests that strengthening extension services, promoting IPM practices, and encouraging soil testing and balanced fertilizer use can help reduce the adoption gap and improve productivity and farmers' income.

Key words: Bt cotton, Adoption gap, Yield gap, Farmers, Constraints

Introduction

Cotton is one of India's most important cash crops and accounts for approximately 22 percent of global fibre production (www.cotcorp.org.in). In India, it is also one of the most important commercial crops. Cotton constitutes approximately 59% of the Indian textile industry's raw material consumption basket. Annual cotton consumption exceeds 300 million bales (170 kg each) (Fernandes, 2022) [4]. In Maharashtra, cotton occupies the largest cultivated area in the country, covering about 41.84 lakh hectares, which accounts for nearly 32.28 per cent of India's total cotton area (129.60 lakh hectares). However, the state ranks second in cotton production with about 86 lakh bales, following Gujarat, and stands ninth in terms of productivity with an average yield of around 319 kg per hectare (ICAC, 2021). The Vidarbha region alone contributes about 39.62 per cent of the cotton area (15.08 lakh hectares) and nearly 44 per cent of the total cotton production of the state, with an average productivity of around 300 kg per hectare. The comparatively low productivity in Maharashtra and the Vidarbha region is mainly attributed to the predominance of rainfed cotton cultivation. Bt cotton is a genetically modified crop, commonly referred to as transgenic cotton. It contains a gene derived from the soil bacterium *Bacillus thuringiensis*, which enables the plant to produce a toxic protein that controls bollworm infestation. This technology helps in reducing the use of insecticides, enhancing crop productivity, improving fiber quality, and providing economic benefits to farmers (Bondarwad et al., 2010). Cotton growers faced several constraints in adopting recommended production technologies, such as irregular rainfall, lack of technical knowledge, high cost of seeds and fertilizers, high labour wages and requirements, non-availability of inputs, and low market price for the produce. (Kamble et al., 2017). Bt cotton technology has positively influenced the socio-economic condition of farmers by increasing crop yield and reducing the cost of inputs. This ultimately leads to higher farm income and improves the overall

standard of living of the farmers. (Gamanagatti and Dodamani (2016).

Objectives

- To study the profile of Bt cotton growers.
- To study the adoption gap and determine yield gap in Bt cotton.
- To identify factor affecting yield gap in Bt cotton.
- To study the relationship between profile of Bt cotton growers and adoption gap in Bt cotton cultivation.
- To identify constraints and invite the suggestion from Bt cotton growers to overcome the adoption gap.

Materials And Methods

The present study entitled "Adoption Gap in Bt Cotton Cultivation" was conducted in Amravati district of the Vidarbha region. Daryapur and Anjangaon Surji tahsils were purposively selected due to their larger area under Bt cotton cultivation. An exploratory research design was used for the study. A total of 12 villages were selected from the chosen tahsils based on the maximum area under Bt cotton crop. From each village, 10 Bt cotton growers were randomly selected, resulting in a total sample of 120 respondents. The required data were collected through personal interviews with the help of a structured interview schedule. The collected data were organized, tabulated, and analyzed using statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and correlation coefficient to interpret the results.

Result And Discussion

The findings of the present study as well as relevant discussion have been presented under following heads.

Profile of Bt cotton growers:

The study of profile of Bt cotton growers was made with reference to age, education, land holding, annual income, area under Bt cotton crop, source of irrigation, farming experience, sources of information, social participation, innovativeness, risk orientation, knowledge. The results have been furnished as follows.

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents according to their profile

(N= 120)

Sr. No.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age		
	Young (up to 35)	28	23.33
	Middle (36 to 55)	41	34.17
	Old (56 and above)	51	42.50
2	Education		
	Illiterate	0	0

	Primary (Up to 4 th Std)	2	1.67
	Middle school (5 th Std. to 7 th Std)	11	9.17
	Secondary education (8 th Std. to 10 th Std)	47	39.17
	Higher secondary (11 th Std and 12 th Std)	39	32.50
	Graduation (Degree and above)	21	17.50
3	Land holding		
	Marginal (up to 1.00 ha)	3	2.50
	Small (1.01 to 2.00 ha)	45	37.17
	Semi-medium (2.01 to 4.00 ha)	41	34.17
	Medium (4.01 to 10.00 ha)	28	23.33
	Large (10.01 ha and above)	3	2.50
4	Annual income		
	Up to Rs. 50,000	21	17.50
	Rs. 50,001 to 1,00,000	39	32.50
	Rs. 1,00,001 to 1,50,000	6	5.00
	Rs. 1,50,001 to 2,00,000	12	10.00
	Above Rs. 2,00,000	42	35.00
5	Area under Bt cotton crop		
	Low (up to 0.85 ha)	6	5.00
	Medium (0.86 to 3.27 ha)	98	81.67
	High (above 3.28 ha)	16	13.33
6	Source of irrigation		
	No Source	61	50.83
	River	0	0.00
	Well	56	46.67
	Canal	3	2.50
7	Farming Experience		
	Low (up to 10 years)	34	28.33
	Medium (11-30 years)	61	50.83
	High (above 31 years)	25	20.83
8	Sources of information		
	Low (up to 9.11)	25	20.83
	Medium (9.12-20.35)	85	70.83
	High (above 20.36)	10	8.33
9	Social Participation		
	Low (up to 1.11)	31	25.83
	Medium (1.12-2.77)	61	50.83
	High (above 2.78)	28	23.33
10	Innovativeness		
	Low (up to 18.05)	21	17.50
	Medium (18.06-22.19)	86	71.67
	High (above 22.20)	13	10.83
11	Risk orientation		
	Low (up to 20.36)	21	17.5
	Medium (20.37-24.98)	69	57.5
	High (above 24.99)	30	25
12	Knowledge		
	Low (up to 9.94)	35	29.17
	Medium (9.95-12.72)	57	47.50
	High (above 12.73)	28	23.33

The major findings of the study indicated that 42.50 per cent of the respondents belonged to the old age group (56 years and above), while 39.17 per cent had education up to secondary level (VIII–X standard). About 37.17 per cent of the respondents were in the small land holding category, and 35.00 per cent had an annual income above Rs. 2,00,000. A large proportion (81.67 per cent) of the respondents had a medium area (0.86–3.27 ha) under Bt cotton cultivation, and 50.83 per cent had no irrigation source. The same percentage (50.83 per cent) of

respondents had medium farming experience and medium social participation, while 70.83 per cent had a medium level of use of information sources. Furthermore, 71.67 per cent of respondents showed a medium level of innovativeness, 57.50 per cent had a medium level of risk orientation, and 47.50 per cent possessed a medium level of knowledge regarding recommended Bt cotton cultivation practices.

Overall adoption gap in Bt cotton cultivation**Table 2. Distribution of Bt cotton growers according to overall adoption gap in recommended Bt cotton cultivation practices**

Sr. No.	Adoption gap	Respondents (n = 120)	
		Frequency	Percentage
1.	Low (up to 29.26)	25	20.83
2.	Medium (29.27-41.72)	74	61.67
3.	High (above 41.72)	21	17.50
Total		120	100.00
Mean = 35.49		S.D. = 6.23	

It is revealed in Table 2 that, 61.67 per cent of Bt cotton growers were observed under medium level category of adoption gap in recommended Bt cotton cultivation practices, followed by 20.83 per

cent of Bt cotton growers were observed in low level of adoption gap and 17.50 per cent in high level of adoption gap in Bt cotton.

Yield gap in Bt cotton**Table 3. Distribution of Bt cotton growers according to yield gap**

Sr. No.	Yield Gap	Respondents (n = 120)	
		Frequency	Percentage
1.	Low (up to 13.38)	21	17.50
2.	Medium (13.39-32.87)	73	60.83
3.	High (above 32.88)	26	21.67
Total		120	100.00
Mean = 22.88		S.D. = 9.70	

It is revealed in Table 3 that, 60.83 per cent of Bt cotton growers were observed under medium level category of yield gap, followed by 21.67 per cent of Bt cotton growers were observed in high level of

yield gap and 17.50 per cent of Bt cotton growers were observed in low level of yield gap.

Factor affecting yield gap**Table 4. Distribution of factor affecting yield gap**

Sr. No.	Factor	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1.	Delayed sowing	48	40	VIII
2.	Imbalanced fertilization	98	81.67	II
3.	Improper plant population	40	33.33	IX
4.	Seed treatment	100	83.33	I
5.	Pest and diseases incidence	68	56.67	V
6.	Lack of awareness about IPM	55	45.83	VII
7.	Non-use of suitable HYV	60	50	VI
8.	Unpredictable weather	80	66.66	IV
9.	Low Soil fertility	35	29.17	X
10.	Weed infestation	82	68.33	III
11.	Lack of knowledge	28	23.33	XI

The table reveals major constraints faced by Bt cotton growers. Seed treatment emerged as the most critical factor (83.33%) ranked first, followed by imbalanced fertilization (81.67%) and weed infestation (68.33%) ranked second and third, respectively. Unpredictable weather (66.66%) was also a major challenge, ranked fourth. Pest and disease incidence affected 56.67% of respondents, occupying the fifth rank. Use of unsuitable HYVs (50%) and lack of awareness about IPM

(45.83%) were moderately reported. Delayed sowing (40%) and improper plant population (33.33%) were comparatively less serious problems. Low soil fertility (29.17%) and lack of knowledge (23.33%) were the least reported constraints. Overall, the findings suggest that technical, environmental, and management-related issues strongly influenced Bt cotton production, with seed-related practices and fertilizer management being the most crucial gaps.

Relational analysis**Table 5. Relationship between profile of respondents with adoption gap of recommended cultivation practices of Bt cotton.**

Sr. No.	Variables	Correlation Coefficient 'r' value's
1	Age	-0.198*
2	Education	0.207*
3	Land holding	-0.210*
4	Annual income	0.202*
5	Area under Bt cotton cultivation	-0.203*
6	Source of irrigation	-0.203*
7	Farming experience	-0.2027*
8	Source of information	0.2020*
9	Social participation	0.016 ^{NS}

10	Innovativeness	0.2065*
11	Risk orientation	-0.165*
12	Knowledge	0.040 ^{NS}
13	Yield gap	0.195*

**Significant at 0.01 per cent level NS- Non- significant

*Significant at 0.05 per cent level

It is depicted in Table 5 that, the correlation analysis shows that age (-0.198), land holding (-0.210), area under Bt cotton cultivation (-0.203), source of irrigation (-0.203), farming experience (-0.2027) and risk orientation (-0.165) had a negative and significant relationship with the adoption gap. On the other hand, education (0.207), annual income (0.202), source of information (0.2020), innovativeness (0.2065) and

knowledge (0.195) showed a positive and significant relationship with the adoption gap. However, social participation (0.016) and risk orientation (0.040) were found to have a non-significant relationship with the adoption gap. Overall, the analysis reveals that several socio-economic and psychological characteristics of farmers significantly influence the adoption gap in Bt cotton cultivation practices.

Constraints faced by the Bt cotton growers and their suggestions to overcome constraints

Table 6. Distribution of respondents according to the constraints faced during use of Bt cotton cultivation practices

Sr. No.	Constraints	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	Costly insecticide	75	62.5	VI
2	High cost of fertilizer	89	74.17	I
3	High cost of labour wages	72	60	VII
4	Lack of labours	77	64.17	IV
5	Low price of cotton offered by market	65	54.17	VIII
6	Lack of Knowledge about cultivation of non-Bt	76	63.33	V
7	Lack of knowledge about proper doses and control measure.	84	70.0	II
8	Non-availability of timely weather forecast.	80	66.67	III

The table 6 shows the distribution of respondents according to the constraints faced during the use of Bt cotton cultivation practices. The major constraint reported by the farmers was high cost of fertilizer (74.17%), which ranked first, followed by lack of knowledge about proper doses and control measures (70.00%) ranked second, and non-availability of timely weather forecast (66.67%) ranked third. Other

constraints included lack of labour (64.17%), lack of knowledge about cultivation of non-Bt (63.33%), costly insecticides (62.50%), and high cost of labour wages (60.00%). The least reported constraint was low price of cotton offered by the market (54.17%). These findings indicate that high input cost and lack of technical knowledge were the major problems faced by Bt cotton growers.

Table 7. Distribution of respondents according to the suggestion given by them.

Sr. No.	Suggestion	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	Promote Integrated Pest Management (IPM), use of pheromone traps, bio-pesticides and need-based spraying to reduce chemical cost.	99	82.50	II
2	Encourage soil testing and balanced fertilizer application; provide subsidy and promote organic manures/biofertilizers.	95	79.16	III
3	Promote farm mechanization (seed drill, sprayer, weeder, cotton picker) through custom hiring centres.	88	77.50	VII
4	Introduce labour-saving implements and group/contract farming practices.	91	75.83	V
5	Ensure Minimum Support Price (MSP) procurement and strengthen regulated market and Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs).	93	77.50	IV
6	Conduct regular training programmes, demonstrations, and field days by extension agencies/KVK.	89	74.17	VI
7	Provide plant protection advisory, pest scouting training and distribute simple crop production literature in local language.	56	46.67	VIII
8	Provide village-level weather-based agro-advisory through SMS, mobile apps, WhatsApp groups and KVK services.	116	96.67	I

It is depicted in Table 7 that the suggestions given by Bt cotton growers to overcome cultivation constraints. The majority of respondents suggested providing village-level weather-based agro-advisory services (96.67%), which ranked first, followed by promotion of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) practices (82.50%) ranked second, and encouraging soil testing and balanced fertilizer application (79.16%) ranked third. Ensuring MSP procurement and strengthening regulated markets and FPOs (77.50%) ranked fourth, while introducing labour-saving implements and contract farming practices (75.83%) ranked fifth. Conducting regular training programmes by extension agencies (74.17%) ranked sixth, and promoting farm mechanization through custom hiring centres (77.50%) ranked seventh. The least suggested measure was providing plant protection advisory and pest scouting training (46.67%), which ranked eighth. These suggestions

indicate the need for improved advisory services, training, and institutional support for Bt cotton farmers.

Conclusion

The study revealed that Bt cotton cultivation in Amravati district shows a noticeable adoption gap in several recommended practices such as proper sowing method, application of FYM, and intercultural operations. Most farmers were observed in the medium adoption gap category, while only a few had low or high gaps. The yield gap indicates that farmers are unable to achieve the potential productivity of Bt cotton due to partial adoption of improved practices. Factors such as education, income, access to information, and innovativeness significantly influenced adoption levels. Farmers also reported constraints like high fertilizer cost, lack of technical knowledge, untimely weather information, and labour shortage. Strengthening

extension services, promoting IPM practices, and encouraging soil testing with balanced fertilizer use can help reduce the adoption gap and improve productivity and farmers' income.

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